

Towards the sustainable giga-factory: developing green cell manufacturing Processes

Work Package 7 D7.2 – First update of the dissemination and communication plan

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Acronyms and abbreviations

AM	Active Materials
BPS	Battery Packs & Systems
CINEA	European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CMEM	Cell manufacturing & equipment manufacturers
DC	Dissemination and Communication
GP	General Public
HE	Horizon Europe
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
OEM	Application & Integration
OS	Open science
PM	Policymakers
RM	Raw Materials
RSL	Recycling / Second Life
R&I	Research and Innovation
SC	Scientific community
SIE	Sustainable innovations
STC	Standardisation Technical Committees
TM	Trade Media
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

GIGAGREEN proposes a structured research plan to develop and scale up novel electrode and cell component manufacturing processes that follow a Design for Manufacturing approach in line with Europe's strategic goal of becoming a global leader in the Li-ion battery value chain.

This means that GIGAGREEN seeks for the minimum environmental impact and energy consumption, cell designs which facilitate the re-use and disassembly, increase of the cost-efficiency and safety of processes and products, and high-throughput technologies able to be easily scaled up and automated in the context of industry 4.0/5.0 gigafactories.

All tasks expected for the period were accomplished on time: social media online (M1), templates and promotional materials (M1), first press release (M1), website released (M2), first newsletter (M3), clustering activities (initiated M5 an ongoing) and attendance to events (M1 and ongoing).

1. Introduction

This document describes the Dissemination and Communication Plan to be adopted by the GIGAGREEN project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to appropriate target communities.

1.2. Context of WP7

The main aim of WP7 is to coordinate the project consortium in the performance of dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities, including IP management. Following the Open Science (OS) approach of the project, partners will maximise the openness of results and the interaction with sectoral stakeholders in a balanced way with IP protection measures established where necessary to ensure the proper exploitation of project KERs. The Consortium will contribute, upon invitation by the CINEA, to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between HE/H2020 supported actions.

1.2. Objectives of T7.1

A detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C) was produced by SIE at the beginning of the project (M6), based on the preliminary indications given in Section 2.2 and in collaboration with all the consortia. It outlines the project's audiences, key messages, and communication channels for dissemination, including roles and responsibilities. The different updates of the plan will offer the monitoring of the different dissemination and communications activities carried out by all partners, evaluated against its KPIs.

2. Objectives

In order to deliver and achieve the outcomes and impacts of the project, GIGAGREEN has set a specific plan for the dissemination, usage, and valorisation of research and innovation results. This document includes outreach efforts to inform the public about the utilisation of European funds for R&I projects, social issues, and the results of a sustainable and cutting-edge cell manufacturing sector in the EU. Thus, improving the communication between science, business, and society. WP7, "Dissemination, exploitation, and communication," will take the lead on these

efforts, liaising with the other partners to ensure the greatest impact is made, and delivering a comprehensive Dissemination, exploitation, and communication Plan by M6. Here is a brief explanation of the main components of this proposal.

3. Target audiences

A sizable list of stakeholders has been initially established by GIGAGREEN for whom the distribution and communication tools and materials will be intended. Although the vehicle manufacturing sector is an established industry, the electric vehicle one and the associated deployment of the cell manufacturing ecosystem in Europe is not. This, which justifies the value chain strategy used in the project, which is typical of fast expanding industries. According to the European Battery Alliance (EBA250.com) Table 1 lists the key players in the value chain along with the key findings that will be shared with them throughout the project.

Table 1: Target groups & contents

Targeted results/content	Target group / Stakeholder
Design to manufacturing guidelines and data driven software / Enhanced cell manufacturing, bringing down costs along the value chain	Raw Materials (RM), Active Materials (AM), Cell manufacturing & equipment manufacturers (CMEM), Battery Packs & Systems (BPS), Application & Integration (OEM, Recycling / Second Life (RSL)
Optimised cell component materials for dry and wet processing / New 3b gen components for high power/energy density	RM, AM, CMEM
Novel wet and dry electrode processing techniques / Demonstrated manufacturing techniques to become market frontrunners in the next 10 years.	CMEM, BPS, OEM
Recycling process / Circular loops enabled within the factory, minimising material inputs	RM, AM, CMEM
Knowledge, reproducibility, etc.	Scientific Community (SC)
Standardisation, public roadmaps actualisation, etc.	Policy Makers (PM), Standardisation Technical Committees (STC)
EC funds, R&I efforts to enable affordable electric mobility.	General Public (GP)
Europe at the forefront of the battery industry, leading gigafactory construction: employment, reducing costs, boosting local and regional economy, etc.	Trade Media (TM)

GIGAGREEN has identified a significant list of target groups to which the dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed, as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1 summarises how the different stakeholder groups will be benefited from the project's results, The dissemination and communication strategy will conduct a thorough value chain analysis to better understand the influence and stakeholder interests, and to better adjust the key messages to deliver and how to do so, increasing the likelihood that the project's findings will be disseminated and used.

GIGAGREEN consortium members have preliminary identified a list of key associations and organisations that will allow to enhance the project's results dissemination through mutual collaboration: [LiPLANET](#) (Network of battery cell Pilot Lines in Europe), [European Battery](#)

Alliance, [EMIRI](#), [ALISTORE](#), [EMMC](#) (European Materials Modelling Council), [BEPA](#) - BATT4EU Partnership, [BATTERY 2030+](#), [European Digital SME Alliance](#), and [ERMA](#) (European Raw Materials Alliance).

Consortium partners are a good reflection of the European battery value chain, including research centers, manufacturers, producers, and academia. Nevertheless, GIGAGREEN's intention is to widen its collaboration with other relevant actors from the industry. Thus, a preliminary stakeholder list was prepared, including more than 300 organisations. This list will be regularly updated, and stakeholders will be informed on the project regular outcomes.

Likewise, similar European and international projects have been identified to seek for synergies: [3beLiEVe](#), [SeNSE](#), [COBRA](#), [HYDRA](#), [MODALIS2](#), [COFBAT H2020](#), [SPIDER](#), [ASTRABAT](#), [Bigmap](#), [BatWoman](#), [greenSPEED](#), [NoVOC](#), [NEXTCELL](#). GIGAGREEN has created a dedicated section on its [website](#), so stakeholders can easily access all their information.

Finally, a set of trade media contacts was listed, including the most relevant magazines: [Autobuild](#), [Autofacil](#), [Automotive news](#), [Autopista](#), [Autovolt](#), [Batteries and energy stories news](#), [Batteries International](#), [Battery Power Magazine](#), [Car and driver](#), [Charged electrical vehicles magazine](#), [Clicacoches.com](#), [Electrek](#), [Electric and hybrid world](#), [Electric cars report](#), [Electric Hybrid vehicles magazine](#), [Electrical India](#), [Energy Magazine Australia](#), [EV Magazine](#), [Inside EVS](#), [KM 77](#), [Motor 16](#), [Motor authority](#), [Motortrend](#). Also, project partners are expected to generate at least 10 peer review articles targeting Journals like [Journal of Materials Chemistry](#) or [Journal of Power Sources](#), as well as the open access site from the EC [Open Research Europe](#).

4. Key messages

The GIGAGREEN project will produce a significant amount of knowledge across five technical WPs, sparking interest across the value chain for cell batteries as well as the vehicle industry. The outputs and messages from produced WPs, as well as the suitable instruments and channels for distribution, must be identified. The essential messages from each WP are displayed in Table 2 below. Additionally, the primary target group(s) and distribution channels are established. The consortium group will keep spreading information about its overall goals and partnership engagement in anticipated activities. This includes private business meetings, presentations to possible clients, and scientific materials, milestones, etc.

Table 2: Key messages

WP	Key message	Target group / Key channels
Design to manufacturing	Digitalisation processes allowing for quicker specification change	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM
Wet and dry processing pathways development	High performance cells in terms of voltage, capacity, life cycle Elimination of organic solvents	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Scale up of the cell manufacturing processes	Cell manufacturing cost reduced by 20% Reduced energy consumption of cell manufacturing by 25%	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM

Electrochemical characterisation, and thermal, ageing and safety tests	Data driven process and product quality control	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Sustainability analyses and recycling process development	Affordable scalable processes	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM

5. Tools and channels

The actions carried out by GIGAGREEN and its results will be disseminated and communicated using a variety of methods and means. The Dissemination Plan will be more effective since each instrument and channel will be used effectively to speak to various target groups at various stages of the project execution. Table 3 shows the connections between the target audiences, the tools and channels, and the anticipated outcomes.

Table 3: Tools and channels

Channels	Tools	Target group	Expected impacts
Printed materials	Brochure	All target groups	Create awareness about the project goals and expected impacts
	Leaflet		
	Poster		
	Rollup		
Online	Website	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM	Keep the audience engaged on the project objectives and outcomes, as well as on achievements, and news.
	Newsletters	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM	
	Social media	GP, AM, RM, SC, PM, CMEM, OEM, TM	
Publications	Scientific papers	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Guarantee knowledge transfer
	Articles	All target groups	Generate interest in the cell battery production and the state-of-the-art technologies developed by GIGAGREEN
	Press releases	TM	Regularly inform trade media on the project outcomes and how this impact positively in European lives in terms of employment, technology development, improvement of environmental footprint, etc
Events organised by GIGAGREEN	Workshops	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Create awareness about the project goals and expected impacts
	Webinars		
Events attended by GIGAGREEN	Conferences	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Keep the audience engaged on the project
	Tradeshows		

			objectives and outcomes, as well as on achievements, and news.
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The project website, articles written for both a lay and technical readership, press releases, e-newsletters, scientific papers and booklets, social media presence, and attendance at workshops and conferences are some of the methods and channels proposed to be employed in this plan.

The dissemination plan described in section 2.2 of the Grant Agreement serves as the foundation for all efforts involving communication with stakeholders outside the project consortium. The goal of journal articles is largely to inform the academic and scientific communities of current discoveries. To spread new pertinent solutions to more potential end consumers, the project will also publish in key trade publications and magazines. The same audience is targeted for project presentations at technical conferences.

The European logo will be displayed along with the disclaimer that the project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe initiative in all dissemination efforts and publications, including the project website. The European emblem will be given the proper prominence when shown alongside a logo.

5.1. Project identity

To build a visual brand, a distinctive project identity has been created (Figure 1). It provides a set of templates that will make it easier to gain a reputation as the project progresses. This involves developing the project's logo and the related style guide. Additional communication materials have been developed and made available on the project [website](#). This includes the project roll-up, poster, factsheet, brochure, and presentation.

Figure 1: GIGAGREEN brand guidelines

5.2. Project website

The GIGAGREEN project [website](#) has been created and it will be continuously updated to be appealing to visitors. It was made available on M2 of the project life and serves as the main repository of the project information and outcomes.

For the time being, it has four main sections:

1. About. This tab contains information on the project goals, approach, and implementation. It also counts on GIGAGREEN's partners' logos and descriptions, as well as the most relevant related initiatives and associations.
2. Downloads. GIGAGREEN has made available the main resources till today: [brochure](#), [poster](#), [factsheet](#), [presentation](#), [logo](#) and [roll up](#). There, visitors can also find the press releases, deliverables and newsletters issued.
3. News. In this section, the project informs stakeholders about the latest updates on the project progress, interviews, and events where partners disseminate GIGAGREEN.
4. Contact. Whoever might be interested in reaching out GIGAGREEN, here they can simply fill out the form and contact the consortia.

5.3. Social media

To ensure greater diffusion to various age groups and target audiences, GIGAGREEN has a social media presence on [X \(formerly Twitter\)](#) and [LinkedIn](#). Social media should be utilised to promote project updates and, most significantly, to increase website traffic.

To broaden reach, GIGAGREEN-related content has been posted often starting in M1 on X and LinkedIn. When the corporate video was created, a YouTube channel was also made available.

To create an audience for the project results, the social media accounts distribute updates about the project’s scope and promote events where GIGAGREEN has been showcased throughout the first phase of the project.

Online media platforms are supervised to gather data on the metrics, sources, content kinds, and people or organisations who support or spread project messaging. This information will enable communication to be targeted and optimised for maximum reach of news or results. The final dissemination report and interim reports will both include these findings. SIE will be responsible for the social media profiles, assisted by partners.

Consortium members will follow and participate as much as they can in the project's social media platforms. The partners will frequently share posts on their own corporate websites and social media platforms. SIE can advise them on the most effective ways to do so if they require support. The key findings, challenges and milestones of the project will be of course communicated (main milestones suitable for promotion can be seen in Table 4 below).

Table 4: Milestones suitable to be communicated

Milestone	WP	Lead partner	Date
Validated Digital Twin	2	Leclanché	M30
Cell component selection	3	CiCe	M33
500 mAh pouch cells	3	CiCe	M43
First batch of 10 reproducible Large 10 Ah cells	4	ABEE	M40
Full cell passing abuse/aging tests	5	Polito	M42
Efficient Recycling Process	6	Inegi	M40

5.4. Printed material

To be distributed at conferences, exhibitions, and other events, as well as to partner networks, a [brochure](#) (Figure 2 and Figure 3), a [poster](#) (Figure 4), a [factsheet](#) (Figure 5), and a [roll-up](#) (Figure 6) have been created. The initial project poster and brochure version include general information regarding the research activities, participants, and anticipated outcomes. Later in the project life, other materials could be created to publicise findings.

Figure 2: GIGAGREEN brochure (page 1)

Figure 3: GIGAGREEN brochure (page 2)

GIGAGREEN proposes a structured research plan to develop and scale up novel electrode and cell component manufacturing processes that follow a Design for Manufacturing approach in line with Europe's strategic goal of becoming a global leader in the Li-ion battery value.

This means that **GIGAGREEN** seeks for the minimum environmental impact and energy consumption, cell designs which facilitate the re-use and disassembly, increase of the cost-efficiency and safety of processes and products, and high-throughput technologies able to be easily scaled up and automated in the context of industry 4.0/5.0 giga-factories.

GIGAGREEN DESIGN FOR MANUFACTURING GIGA-FACTORY CONCEPT

 SAFER - Elimination of organic solvents	 CHEAPER - Reduced energy and material consumption, economy of scale - Cell manufacturing cost reduced by 20%	 GREENER - Reduced energy and material consumption - Energy consumption of cell manufacturing reduced by 25%	 FLEXIBLE - Digitalization processes allowing to quicker specification change - Affordable scalable process	 BETTER - High performance cells in terms of voltage, capacity, life cycle - Data-driven process and product quality control
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GIGAGREEN will finalise by the end of the project with a set of novel materials (binders, electrolyte, separators, cathode, and anode active materials, etc.), adapted to innovative dry and wet electrode processing techniques, which motivate the generation of Design for Manufacturing guidelines and a data-driven Digital Twin.

GIGAGREEN proposes a sustainable and cost-efficient new approach by integrating synergies and materials within the recycling and production chain of the new battery systems. Apart from recycling the metals (Cu, Ni and Al) and plastics, **GIGAGREEN** aims to recycle both active materials and electrolyte.

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www.gigagreenproject.eu @GIGAGREEN [gigagreen-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/gigagreen-project)

Figure 4: GIGAGREEN poster

Figure 5: GIGAGREEN factsheet

GIGAGREEN

TOWARDS THE SUSTAINABLE GIGA-FACTORY:

Developing green cell manufacturing processes

nanomakers manz SINTEF

Sustainable INNOVATIONS Leclanché Energy Storage Solutions ARLANXEO Performance Elastomers

ineqi driving science & innovation ALPhA NOV Centre Technologique Optique et Lasers ABEE LASER ENERGY & ENERGY ENGINEERING

SOLVIONIC UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA Politecnico di Torino

UNIVERSITÀ DI PARMA CIC energI GUNE MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

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Figure 6: GIGAGREEN roll-up

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5.5. Newsletters and press releases

Every six months, electronic newsletters containing project updates, news, interviews, and other GIGAGREEN-related information have been created. These newsletters are sent to stakeholders and partner networks as well as uploaded on the project website.

Additionally, project updates could be included in the partners' own newsletters, which are sent electronically to the contacts they have within the relevant industries.

Press releases have been and will be released to announce noteworthy project advancements as they happen. With the support of the project partners, they are written in English and distributed to the national media and the European press.

5.6. Peer-reviewed articles

The technical and academic partners will create at least 10 scientific papers, bringing additional benefits like greater transparency in the research process, better opportunities for new scientific collaborations, and increased efficiencies in research. The project's findings will be disseminated both internationally in international journals like [Journal of Materials Chemistry](#) or [Journal of Power Sources](#), as well as nationally, primarily in the Member States where the partners are based. Open Research Europe is an open-access, free-of-cost alternative as well for partners.

Likewise, the project website will compile all publications and make them available for free download.

5.7. Conferences and events

To meet target audiences, other stakeholders, public authorities, and the scientific community, project partners will attend sector-related events, conferences, and workshops. They will also spread the word about the project's goals and outcomes. Access to target audiences at the local, national, European, and worldwide levels will be made possible by these events.

The following conferences and trade shows have been pointed out as being of interest to the GIGAGREEN project:

- [31 & 32 LCE Conference](#). June 2024 & 2025
- [Therminic](#). September 2024
- [E MOVE 360° EUROPE](#). October 2024
- [World Energy Congress](#). October 2024
- [Thermal management for EV/EHV](#). November 2024
- [Future Battery Forum](#). November 2024
- [Battery Innovation Days](#). November 2024
- [Battery Tech Expo](#). January 2025
- [Energy Storage Summit](#). February 2025
- [Vehicle Electrification Expo](#). July 2025
- [E-Tech Europe](#). April 2025
- [The Battery Show Europe](#). June 2025.

In order to ensure that the project is present at events for dissemination, this list of events will be updated often in partnership with the consortia.

Along with attending conferences and trade shows, GIGAGREEN will collaborate with other initiatives under the same call to host at least two workshops by the end of the project to address standardisation and policies, as well as four other webinars to raise awareness on the different project propositions.

5.8. Indicators and targets

The accomplishment of particular targets for various indicators (shown in Table 5) will serve as a gauge for how well the Dissemination and Communication Plan is being implemented.

Table 5: Indicator and targets

Tools / channel	Indicator	Target number	Information source	Status
Brochure Poster Factsheet	Number of copies distributed	Material distribution: <300 poor; 300-500 good; >500 excellent	Consortium information, number of copies distributed to target groups / stakeholders	625 (excellent)
Website	Number of visits	Visits per year: <600 poor; 600 – 1,200 good; >1,200 excellent	Website statistics	1,543 (last 12 months) (excellent)
Social media (X, LinkedIn)	Number of followers of Number of impressions Engagement rate	X; (a) Followers: < 100 poor; 100 – 200 good; > 200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <0.2% poor; 0.2% - 0.9% good; > 0.9% excellent LinkedIn; (a) Followers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <2% poor; 2- 3% good; >3% excellent	Social media analytics	X: 260 followers 7.08 % ER (excellent) LinkedIn: 826 followers 7.60 % ER (excellent)
Videos	Number of views Audience in conferences / trade shows	At least 2 in the project. Views: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent	YouTube, website and social media analytics Attendance to booth /conference	267 views (excellent)

Newsletters	Number of subscribers Number of opens Visits from website / social media	At least one each six months. Subscribers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >300 excellent Opens: <15% poor; 15% – 17% good; >17% excellent	Mailchimp (newsletter service), Website and social media analytics	4 newsletters 255 subscribers (average) 38,30% open rate (average) (excellent)
Press releases	Number of media stakeholders addressed Number of views on website and social media	At least 4. 100 media sources / journalists reached Number of views: < 40 = poor; 40-60 = good; >60 = excellent	Recording of e-mails sent, Website and social media analytics	2 PRs 200 media reached per PR (excellent)
Scientific publications	Number of views/downloads	10 publications	Link to site where posted or PDF version of article	2 publications
Workshops	Number of attendees	1 standardisation + 1 policy feedback workshop. Number of attendees each: <15 = poor; 15-25 = good; >25 = excellent	Registration list	TBD
Webinars		4 webinars. Number of attendees: <25 = poor; 25-45 = good; >45 = excellent	Registration list /webinar platform analytics	TBD
Conferences Trade fairs	Number of conferences and trade fairs attended Number of exhibitors and participants	Attend 24 conferences	Certificate of participation; Proof of registration; Event information	19

6. Levels of dissemination

The geographic levels at which the main target groups operate will affect the communication methods and media used.

6.1. European Level – European Commission

The results of the project will be reported to the EC on a regular basis (mid-term review, minutes of periodic meetings, updates to this document) so that it can make any necessary changes to the relevant regulations and suggest collaborating with other projects that are already in progress on dissemination efforts.

6.2. International level – Industry, Scientific community

The outcomes will be communicated to the pertinent international organisations. Scientific knowledge can be converted into useful information, regulations, and guidelines. Electronic resources will be distributed by direct mailing to specified organisations and stakeholders in order to increase public awareness.

For the transmission of knowledge at both the research and industrial levels, technical journals, conferences, and workshops at both the national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be utilised.

7. Strategies

To make sure that the GIGAGREEN outcomes are effectively and efficiently conveyed to the project partners, stakeholders, and wider audiences, the following internal and external communication activities will be carried out throughout the project's duration and afterward.

7.1. Internal Communication

To effectively share information and guarantee that the deliverables are met, effective internal communication is essential. Therefore, to exchange project information, update progress, and share outcomes, frequent meetings and conference calls will be held. Two times a year, consortium and technical meetings will be held, and WP collaboration will be facilitated through the use of Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing tools.

Apart from individual emails, taking advantage of the project monthly conference call, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination Plan and expedite a content curating process. As a result, the partners will be better able to communicate and report on the project while also adopting a more methodical and focused approach. Each GIGAGREEN consortium partner will send a representative to this meeting.

Politecnico di Torino has also set up a Microsoft SharePoint space, which will host the project materials for internal use, including regular updates on the project development, meeting documents (agenda, minutes, and presentations), and project reports. This will help partners communicate effectively with one another.

A login name and password will be required to access this exclusive area.

7.2. External communication

The consortium will make every effort to spread the word about its activities through the media, journals, conference presentations, trade shows, workshops, the Commission, and industry associations. The project's findings will be published in reports, academic publications, and articles. To encourage scientific collaboration, all public communications and scientific publications shall be made open access.

The partners will send SIE the text whenever a translation is required, and SIE will take care of modifying the design.

8. Methodology

As the project has different development phases, the communication focus would be different across each of them.

8.1. Phase 1: Awareness phase

In this phase, GIGAGREEN will prioritise the generation of a community of interested stakeholders and of suitable channels. It will comprise from months 1 to 12.

8.2. Phase 2: Scientific cooperation phase

This second phase will consist of knowledge management for the cooperation of GIGAGREEN with similar projects and initiatives and ensuring the availability of research outputs to targeted audience. It will start in M6 and will last for the project duration.

8.3. Phase 3: Exploitation-focused phase

This phase will cover the support to the actual exploitation of project results via marketing towards final end users (commercial results) or workshops and roadmaps (non-commercial results) and will comprise the final stages of the project (M24-M48).

9. Activities

9.1. Project identity and materials

The project identity initially established, and that was explained and shown in the first Dissemination and Communication plan (D7.1), as well as in section 5.1 of this document, has been, of course, followed in this period of the project, to create a recognisable, homogeneous brand image. Examples of this can be seen in different communication resources (that will be explained further in the deliverable), such as the pictures that illustrate the web posts (Figure 7), the video interviews (Figure 8) or the newsletters' style (Figure 9).

Figure 7: Web posts images

Figure 8: Screenshot of a video interview

Towards the sustainable gigafactory: developing green cell manufacturing processes

Figure 9: GIGAGREEN's fourth newsletter

The communication materials (brochure, poster, project presentation) that were made public in M2 to the audience through the website, have been updated to match linguistic technical accuracy. Concretely, technical partners noticed that in the materials, the term “Design to Manufacture” was being used. They expressed that, while it is correct, the most used term (and therefore, the standardised one) is “Design for Manufacturing”. A show of this can be seen in Figure 10 below, where it appears the term highlighted in the new version of the brochure.

Figure 10: New version of the brochure with the new term highlighted

Regarding the PowerPoint and Word templates, they were kept in the initial format, as no changes were required. SIE, as WP managers, will pay attention to further changes in the project's scope,

methodology or composition, and will evaluate if those changes affect to the brand guidelines, the communication materials or the templates and will require any change.

9.2. Press releases

After the first successful press release about the project's kick-off that was echoed in 74 media (as can be seen in Annexe 1: Impact on media outlets and other relevant websites M1-M24), social media profiles and webpage, a second one (Figure 11) was sent. It announced the participation of GIGAGREEN in the Transport Research Arena (TRA) 2024 (explained below) along with the rest of the projects that form the Battery Heroes cluster was released. It was sent to more than 1000 media. Although this massive sending, the news was only published by [WIT News](#).

GIGAGREEN Project Joins Forces with other three EU-funded projects at Transport Research Arena 2024

- TRA 2024, Europe's leading transport event, themed "Transport Transitions: Advancing Sustainable and Inclusive Mobility," will take place in Dublin, Ireland from April 15 to 18.
- The Battery Heroes clustering, formed by GIGAGREEN, NoVoc, BatWoman and GREENSPEED projects, will have a booth where advances and aims in the battery innovation field will be presented.

Turin, Italy, March 26th 2024. GIGAGREEN, an EU-funded project that aims to develop and scale up novel electrode and cell component manufacturing processes that follow a Design to Manufacture approach will be present at Transport Research Arena 2024. GIGAGREEN is part, along with another three sister projects (NoVoc, BatWoman and GREENSPEED), of a clustering initiative called Battery Heroes, whose aim is to foster advances and innovations from the battery research environment.

At TRA 2024, GIGAGREEN will showcase its progress in advancing a suite of novel materials, including binders, electrolytes, separators, cathode, and anode active materials. These materials are tailored to innovative dry and wet electrode processing techniques, paving the way for the creation of Design to Manufacture guidelines and a data-driven Digital Twin.

The Transport Research Arena (TRA) stands as Europe's primary transportation gathering, encompassing every mode of transport and facet of mobility, as well as the premier European conference dedicated to research and technology in transportation and mobility. It will take place in Dublin, Ireland, from April 15 to 18. TRA provides a pivotal platform for researchers, policymakers, and industry delegates to collaborate on reshaping transport and mobility through research and innovation, fostering knowledge exchange on European mobility trends, industry achievements, and policy implementations.

This encounter will be an opportunity for the four projects to create even more synergies, disseminate their early results and communicate their aims, as well as to stay in contact with different stakeholders from the entire battery value chain. A special space will be created for young scientists and students, who will be able to learn from the technical experts involved in the projects and get to know the current innovations in the field.

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement N° 101069707. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 11: TRA Press Release

9.3. Website

The website, that was launched at M2, has been updated periodically as soon as new information emerges from the project. The most usually updated section is the “News” one, where the following 24 posts have been uploaded:

1. [SOLVIONIC ATTENDS THE WORLD SMART ENERGY WEEK](#)
2. [GIGAGREEN AT THE EVENT NOUVELLE AQUITAINE BATTERY DAY](#)
3. [INTERVIEW WITH MARIANA FERNÁNDEZ](#)
4. [GIGAGREEN PRESENT AT E-TECH EUROPE 2023](#)
5. [INTERVIEW WITH LUCA SCHNEIDER](#)
6. ["LASER-TEXTURING OF CURRENT COLLECTORS WILL BE EMPLOYED TO REDUCE INTERFACE RESISTANCE AND THUS IMPROVING CELL LIFESPAN"](#)
7. [POLITO PARTICIPATES IN A WORKSHOP HOSTED BY THE HORIZON 2020 HYDRA PROJECT](#)
8. ["OUR MAIN GOAL IS TO OPTIMISE THE ANODE MATERIAL COMPOSITE TO REACH A STABILITY OF MORE THAN 500 CYCLES"](#)
9. ["BY USING LASERS, THE SURFACE PERFORMANCE WILL BE BOOSTED, TRANSFORMING THUS THE MATERIAL INTO A SMART MATERIAL"](#)
10. [CETIM IS DESIGNING A DIGITAL TWIN BASED ON A SIMULATION MODEL MADE WITH AI TO MAKE THE SCALE-UP OF THE BATTERIES MANUFACTURING PROCESS POSSIBLE"](#)
11. [GIGAGREEN HOLDS ITS SECOND GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN TRONDHEIM, NORWAY](#)
12. ["COLLECTING DATA TO SUPPORT THERMAL RUNAWAY MODELS AND VERIFYING COMPLIANCE WITH SAFETY STANDARDS ARE CRUCIAL ASPECTS OF THE TESTING PROCESS"](#)
13. [POLITO PARTICIPATES IN ABAF 2023](#)
14. [GIGAGREEN, PRESENT AT BATTERIES EVENT 2023](#)
15. [GIGAGREEN, AT THE BATTERY INNOVATION DAYS](#)
16. [GIGAGREEN AND THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS. SDG 9: INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE](#)
17. [GIGAGREEN AND THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS. SDG 13: CLIMATE ACTION](#)
18. [BATTERY HEROES: COLLABORATING FOR A GREENER BATTERY PRODUCTION](#)
19. [GIGAGREEN AND THE BATTERY HEROES, AT THE RTR CONFERENCE](#)
20. [SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS DISSEMINATES GIGAGREEN AT GENERA](#)
21. [GIGAGREEN AND THE BATTERY HEROES, AT THE TRANSPORT RESEARCH ARENA 2024](#)
22. [GIGAGREEN AND THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS: SDG7 – AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY](#)
23. [GIGAGREEN, PRESENTED AT LPM 2024](#)
24. [GIGAGREEN AND THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS: SDG12 – RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION](#)

The “Downloads” section has also been updated every time that material has been published from the project. It counts 18 documents:

- 6 marketing materials from the project
- 2 marketing materials from the Battery Heroes clustering
- 2 press releases
- 4 newsletters
- 2 scientific publications
- 2 public deliverables.

In the M7-M23 period, the website received a total of 1,543 unique visits (a “good” target, following the KPIs), an engagement rate of 68.05% (almost the same as until M6, that was of 68.65% and

the average session duration of the visitors was 17:06 minutes (much longer than the one until M6, that was 2:56 minutes), all the figures and some more are shown in Figure 12. The total number of visits in the website's lifetime is 2,003.

Figure 12: M7-M23 Website statistics

The project's website was presented to the [.eu Web Awards](#). In June it was announced that it was nominated for the award, and a campaign to encourage votation was launched (an example from LinkedIn can be seen in Figure 13). Although the effort that was made, the website was not finally awarded.

Figure 13: Campaign encouraging the vote for the EURid's Web Awards

Last, the website was evaluated using the [Green Web Foundation's app](#), confirming it uses green hosting. Consequently, a badge was added to the footer to reflect this (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: GIGAGREEN's website footer with the Green Hosting badge

9.4. Social Media

The social media channels have been regularly updated to maintain audience engagement. Weekly updates on X (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn ensure a steady stream of new content and interaction. Although updates temporarily slow down during holiday periods like August or Christmas, this approach has successfully established an active community of followers.

GIGAGREEN has 826 followers on LinkedIn by the end of month 23 (Figure 15). 110 posts have been uploaded (73 between M7 and M23). The engagement rate (7.6%) means an "excellent" performance following the KPIs Table 5. The posts gained, altogether, 106,971 impressions (increasing in 91,119 in the period between M6 and M23).

Figure 15: GIGAGREEN's LinkedIn

On X, the project counts with 260 followers by the end of M23 (Figure 16), and also 110 posts (73 between M6 and M23) have been uploaded. When checking the KPIs, the engagement rate (7.08%) is also excellent. There is an average impressions/month of a 1,229.

Figure 16: GIGAGREEN's X

A YouTube account was created in M7 (Figure 17) when the project's official video was released. The official video counts with 260 views by M23. Since then, another two video campaigns (explained below) have also been added to this social network: the Battery Heroes official video and the WP leaders' interviews.

GIGAGREEN Project

@gigagreenproject · 6 subscribers · 7 videos

GIGAGREEN proposes a structured research plan to develop and scale up novel electrode ...more

gigagreenproject.eu and 2 more links

Subscribe

Home Videos Playlists

Videos ▶ Play all

Figure 17: GIGAGREEN's YouTube channel

9.5. Newsletters

Until M23, four newsletters have been sent to the GIGAGREEN's audience, which makes a total of four newsletters released during the entire project. The first newsletter (Figure 18) announced the kick-off and was sent in M3 to an audience of 258 recipients, and had an open rate of 42.64%. The second one (Figure 19) was sent in M9, to an audience of 258 recipients, and had an open rate of 37.98%. The fourth was sent in M15, to an audience of 255 recipients, and had an open rate of 35.20% (Figure 20). The last one was sent in M22, to an audience of 255 recipients, and had an open rate of 36.86% (Figure 21).

Figure 18: First newsletter

Figure 19: GIGAGREEN's second newsletter

Towards the sustainable gigafactory: developing green cell manufacturing processes

GIGAGREEN project's partners reunited for the general assembly in Trondheim (Norway) on September 4 and 5.

GIGAGREEN: One Year of Advancing Sustainable Battery Manufacturing

After its initiation in September 2022, GIGAGREEN has successfully completed its first year. To commemorate this achievement, all project partners came together for a consortium meeting in Trondheim.

There, they reviewed the work and activities accomplished in the past year and discussed the plans for the upcoming year.

Figure 20: GIGAGREEN's third newsletter

Figure 21: GIGAGREEN's fourth newsletter

9.6. Events attended

Partners have promoted GIGAGREEN in the events shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Events attended by GIGAGREEN partners

#	Name	Date	Partner(s) that participated	Link
1	NanoInnovation.	September 2022.	CICe energigUNE	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1039
2	Kunststoffe für Brennstoff Zellen und modern Batterietechnik (Plastics for fuel cells and modern battery technology)	November 2022	Arlanxeo	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1323
3	Wired Italia Trends	December 2022.	Politécnico di Torino	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7006212610467491840/
4	Battery Day Nouvelle Aquitaine.	February 2023	Alphanov	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1356

5	RTR conference 2023	February 2023	Politécnico di Torino	https://twitter.com/GIGAGREEN_/status/1668567826511060992
6	World Smart Energy Week	March 2023	Solvionic	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1350
7	E-TECH EUROPE 2023	April 2023	Manz	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1376
8	2030+ Annual Conference	May 2023	Politécnico di Torino	https://twitter.com/GIGAGREEN_/status/1666049043284340737
9	Horizon 2020 Hydra Project's workshop	June 2023	Politécnico di Torino, SINTEF and Solvionic	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1435
10	100 Italian mobility stories	July 2023	Politécnico di Torino	https://twitter.com/GIGAGREEN_/status/1681253478902153216
11	ABAF 2023	August 2023	Politécnico di Torino	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1458
12	Batteries Event	October 2023	Solvionic	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1462
13	EPIC meeting	October 2023	Alphanov	https://twitter.com/GIGAGREEN_/status/1731981285839524071
14	Battery Innovation Days	November 2023	Politécnico di Torino, Manz, ABEE and Alphanov	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1466
15	RTR Brussels	February 2024	Politécnico di Torino	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1508
16	Genera	February 2024	Sustainable Innovations	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1513
17	Transport Research Arena	April 2024	Politécnico di Torino	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1526
18	LPM 2024	June 2024	Alphanov	https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1550
19	Hyceltec 2024	June-July 2024	Politécnico di Torino	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/silvia-bodoardo-5a38301_thank-you-hyceltec-conference-in-milazzo-activity-7214499426319421447-ol3f?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

Apart from this list, it is worth mentioning that in June 2023, UPV organised a [students' visit to the university facilities](#). There, Professor Carlos Micó Reche introduced the students the safety test equipment used as part of the activities UPV carries out for GIGAGREEN.

9.7. Interaction with other EU initiatives

The interaction with the projects under the same call established at the beginning of the project and named Battery Heroes, has continued, being fruitful and proactive. The Battery Heroes grew in members, and [BATMACHINE](#), and [GIGABAT](#) were added to the group, initially compounded by GIGAGREEN and three other projects: [NoVoc](#), [greenSPEED](#), and [BatWoman](#). The clustering group held meetings every month, and several actions that have been taken or are going to take place were discussed:

- A joint internal [workshop](#) was held in person in San Sebastian (Spain), and Laida Otaegui, WP leader of WP3, attended physically.

- The application to the Horizon Results Booster, an EC's service to help clustering groups to further promote. This service did a promotional video, as it is explained in section 13.8 below.
- Attendance to the RTR Conference, where Silvia Bodoardo, GIGAGREEN's coordinator, presented the clustering group.
- The creation of a common basic brand identity (logo and colours) and communication materials such as a brochure (Figure 22) and a roll-up (Figure 23).
- Attendance to the TRA Conference in Dublin, in April, where the four projects shared a booth and displayed a "Meet the Experts" session where Silvia Bodoardo (POLITO) was included.
- Planning and execution of a workshop on Life Cycle Assessment. The idea of developing this workshop appeared in GIGAGREEN's monthly meeting, as the partners in charge of this topic were facing challenges. The workshop happened on July, 10th, and counted 8 participants from all the projects.
- Planning of a workshop with LiPLANET, entitled "Sustainable Electrode/Cell Production Workshop" that will happen on September 19th in Braunschweig (Germany). The invitation sent by email can be seen in Figure 24.

Figure 22: Battery Heroes brochure

Figure 23: Battery Heroes roll-up.

Figure 24: Invitation to LiPLANET & Battery Heroes workshop

9.8. Video campaigns

As have been mentioned above, three video campaigns have been or are being implemented. The first one was the official project video, an animation made by SIE, that requested collaboration to all the consortium partners for reviewing the script. The video was uploaded to YouTube on M7, and it was promoted on the project's social media (this post was pinned to the top of both X and LinkedIn profiles for some months) and uploaded to the main page of the project's website (as can be seen in Figure 25).

Figure 25: The official project video on the website

As mentioned in section 13.7, the Horizon Results Booster produced also a video promoting the Battery Heroes initiative. A first and a second draft were shared with all the members of the cluster, who gave their feedback on both versions. After several email exchanges and a feedback call, the final video was launched. It was promoted by GIGAGREEN on social media (an example can be seen on Figure 26).

Figure 26: Battery Heroes video promotion on LinkedIn

The last video campaign was launched recently and is still being promoted. It consists of 5 videos where the leaders of the technical work packages of the project explain briefly the work that they carry out in their WP. Four of them were recorded by SIE in the project's general assembly in Ninove (Belgium). The other one was recorded recording a Microsoft Teams call, as this WP leader couldn't manage to go to this meeting due to conflicts on his agenda. The five videos have been uploaded to YouTube as a playlist (as shown in Figure 27) and will be promoted through the project's social media.

Figure 27: Playlist on YouTube with the 5 WP leaders' videos

9.9. Scientific contributions

Two papers have been published in this period, showing the project's findings and methodology. Both papers have been published following the Open Science principles, so are accessible to anyone in an open repository. As mentioned above (section 13.3), both articles were uploaded to the website:

- "[Nanosecond pulsed laser texturing of Li-ion battery electrode current collectors: Electrochemical characterisation of cathode half-cells](#)" was published by Politecnico di Torino in *Sustainable Materials and Technologies*.
- "[Benefits of Femtosecond Laser 40 MHz Burst Mode for Li-Ion Battery Electrode Structuring](#)" was published by Alphanov in *Materials*.

10. Conclusions

The GIGAGREEN dissemination and communication plan has set the basis that has led the project to success towards achieving communication and dissemination goals in its first 24-month period. By targeting a broad spectrum of stakeholders using a variety of tools, such as social media, the website, or physical materials (brochures or posters, for example), the consortium has ensured the promotion of the project, its objectives and challenges. The clustering group formed with Battery Heroes, as well as the high attendance to events, both scientific and industry-related, further amplified the project's visibility and impact.

Looking ahead, the plan provides a robust framework for continued dissemination, ensuring that GIGAGREEN's advancements in sustainable cell manufacturing reach scientific, industrial, and public audiences. The future refinement of communication strategies and the focus on key milestones, as well as what we call the "Exploitation-focused phase" (described in section 8.3), will serve the communication objectives that GIGAGREEN has. A broader adoption of the project's outcomes is expected, as well as the activation of new discussions within the scientific community, reinforcing Europe's leadership in sustainable battery production.

Annexe 1: Impact on media outlets and other relevant websites M1-M24

ABEE

<https://abeegroup.com/projects/>

ACLIMA

<https://aclima.eus/gigagreen-un-proyecto-europeo-de-raiz-gallega-para-construir-gigafabricas-de-baterias-sostenibles/>

ALPHANOV

<https://www.alphanov.com/projets-collaboratifs/projet-gigagreen>

AGADIR GROUP

<https://agadir-group.com/gigagreen-consortium-designs-future-battery-cell-factories/>

ALL INFO

<https://allinfo.space/2022/09/22/the-gigagreen-project-for-the-gigafactories-of-the-future-is-underway-italy-at-the-forefront/>

ANSA PIEMONTE

https://www.ansa.it/piemonte/notizie/2022/09/22/politecnico-torino-al-via-progetto-ue-gigagreen_c16a660a-c998-4b15-85a2-066d7ab15413.html

ATIGA

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/atiga_la-upv-participa-en-un-proyecto-europeo-activity-6975743396543913984-NnoV?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

AUTOREVISTA

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/autorevista_gigagreen-sentar%C3%A1-las-bases-para-construir-activity-6975777445769568256-ZK4b?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

<https://www.auto-revista.com/texto-diario/mostrar/3888764/gigagreen-sentara-bases-construir-gigafabricas-baterias-ion-li-sostenibles>

BATTERIES NEWS

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/batteriesnews_sustainable-innovations-universitat-politecnica-activity-6975489949420666880-XPsb?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

<https://batteriesnews.com/sustainable-innovations-universita>

t-politecnica-de-valencia-cic-energigune-cetim-technological-center-partners-gigagreen-project-seeking-gigafactory-future-li-ion-battery-c/

<https://twitter.com/BatteriesNews/status/1569724529387110401>

BATTERY POWER ONLINE

<https://www.batterypoweronline.com/news/battery-funding-research-updates-more-sept-2022/>

BESTMAG

<https://www.bestmag.co.uk/automotive-skills-alliance-and-european-battery-alliance-academy-join-forces-to-bridge-battery-supply-chain-skills-gap/>

CANAL ENERGÍA

<https://www.canalenergia.com/rubriche/think-tech/trasferire-produzione-di-batterie-da-asia-a-europa-al-via-gigagreen/>

CETIM

<https://cetim.es/gigagreen-hacia-la-gigafabrica-de-baterias-sostenible/?lang=en>

<https://cetim.es/gigagreen-hacia-la-gigafabrica-de-baterias-sostenible/>

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cetim-technological-centre_gigagreen-towards-the-sustainable-battery-activity-6975776825335525376-fdp3?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

CIC energiGUNE

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6975383561365254144/?actorCompanyId=86576618>

<https://cicenergigune.com/en/news/cic-energigune-european-project-battery-cell-green-manufacturing>

<https://cicenergigune.com/es/noticias/cic-energigune-proyecto-europeo-gigagreen-fabricacion-verde-celdas-bateria>

<https://cicenergigune.com/eu/berriak/cic-energigune-gigagreen-proiektu-europarra-bateria-gelaxka-fabrikazio-berdea>

<https://cicenergigune.com/en/news/cicenergigune-green-light-europe-scientific-proposals-horizon-call-batteries>

<https://cicenergigune.com/es/noticias/cicenergigune-luz-verde-propuestas-cientificas-convocatoria-horizonte-europa-baterias>

<https://cicenergigune.com/eu/berriak/europa-argi-berdea-bateria-horizonte-europa-deialdia-cicenergigune-proposamen-zientifikoak>

CN TECHNODE

<https://cn.technode.com/post/2022-09-15/gigagreen-ev/>

ECOMENTO

<https://ecomento.de/2022/09/22/gigagreen-konsortium-will-akkufabriken-der-zukunft-entwerfen/>

ELBILEN

<https://elbilen.se/nyheter/gigagreen-projekt-for-hallbar-batteritillverkning-i-eu/>

ELECTRIVE

<https://www.electrive.com/2022/09/13/gigagreen-consortium-designs-future-battery-cell-factories/>

<https://www.electrive.net/2022/09/13/gigagreen-konsortium-entwirft-zellfabriken-der-zukunft/>

ELECTRO AUTO NEWS

<https://www.elektroauto-news.net/2022/giga-fabrik-der-zukunft-in-europa-entwickelt>

ELECTROTRANSPORTE

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/electrotransporte-p%C3%A1gina-oficial_proyecto-europeo-gigagreen-propone-mejorar-activity-6975568763626610688-oZXc?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

<https://electrotransporte.com.pe/noticias/proyecto-europeo-gigagreen-propone-mejorar-los-procesos-de-produccion-de-celdas-de-bateria/>

EL PERIODIC

https://www.elperiodic.com/valencia/universitat-politecnica-valencia-participa-proyecto-europeo-gigagreen-busqueda-gigafactoria-futuro_848036

ENERGIA MERCATO

<https://www.energiamercato.it/notizie/nuova-mobilita/gigagreen-politecnico-torino>

ENERGY NEWS

<https://www.energynews.es/gigagreen-proyecto/>

ESTRATEGIA.NET

<https://twitter.com/Estrategianet/status/1569633409240297474>

EV Magazine

<https://www.ev-magazine.com/the-gigagreen-project-kicks-off-to-achieve-the-future-sustainable-giga-factory/>

GESTOR DE RESIDUOS

<https://gestoresderesiduos.org/noticias/gigagreen-un-proyecto-europeo-de-raiz-gallega-para-construir-gigafabricas-de-baterias-sostenibles>

GREEN START UP

<https://green.start-up.ro/en/european-officials-want-more-sustainable-batteries-for-the-eu-market/>

HD MOTOR

<https://www.hdmotori.it/auto/articoli/n561247/gigagreen-progetto-gigafactory-sostenibile-italia/>

INGENIEROS.es

<https://www.ingenieros.es/noticias/ver/proyecto-gigagreen-la-upv-participa-en-un-proyecto-para-la-produccion-sostenible-de-baterias-de-iones-de-litio/8532>

INNEWS.EU

<https://ineews.eu/comissao-europeia-financia-9-projetos-portugueses-inovadores-com-57-milhoes-de-euros/>

INSIDEEVS

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INSTITUTO MOTORES TÉCNICOS

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